

INFLUENCE OF GENDER ON EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AMONG SPORTS PLAYERS OF PATNA UNIVERSITY

Kundan kumar¹ & Dr. Vitahl Ramkishan Bhosale²

¹ Ph.D. Research Scholar, Physical Education Department, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Aurangabad, Maharashtra

² Assistant Professor, Shri Panditguru Pardikar Mahavidyalaya, Sirsala, Beed, Maharashtra

Paper Received On: 12 December 2023

Peer Reviewed On: 28 January 2024

Published On: 01 February 2024

Abstract

The present research study throwing the light on the influence of gender on the psychological variable emotional intelligence among sports players of Patna University, Patna. The researcher refereed the many related studies before conduct the investigation, the major aim and objectives of the present study are as follows: - To check the emotional intelligence among sports players of Patna University, To collect the research data of emotional intelligence through the standard scale from sample of the study, and Compare the emotional intelligence among male and female sports players to compare the influence of gender. The sample were selected through the simple random method of sampling from the constituent colleges of Patna university, Patna. The investigator took one hundred inter-collegiate participated players as sample of the study who have represented the inter collegiate sports meet at college level, the sample consisted both male and female sports players in equal number. The research data was calculated through the SPSS package to find out the results of the study. The research hypothesis stated that- There would be influence of gender on the emotional intelligence of sports players and there would be significance difference in emotional intelligence among sports players.

Keywords: Gender, Emotion, Emotional Intelligence.

Introduction

The emotional Intelligence is the one of the most importance psychological factor in the human personality. Traditionally, psychologists have focused on cognitive aspects while working on intelligence. However, there were researchers who recognized early that the non-cognitive aspects were also important. The most distant roots of emotional intelligence can be traced to Charles Darwin's (1872) early work on the importance of emotional expression for survival and second adaptation. The control over the self-emotions and also understand the others feelings with same respect. The person who can understand the situations and ready to handle every person with the disturbance of mind. It is the ability to handle the self and others mental situations. There are many models and definitions on Emotional Intelligence. Let us discuss some of the most important definitions of the concept.

According to Goleman, emotional intelligence is "the capacity for recognizing our own feelings and those of others, for motivating ourselves, and for managing emotions well in ourselves and in our

¹ Ph.D. Research Scholar, Physical Education Department, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada university, Aurangabad, Maharashtra

² Assistant Professor, Shri Panditguru Pardikar Mahavidyalaya, Sirsala, Beed, Maharashtra

relationships” (Goleman, 1998a, p.375). He describes EI as complementary and yet distinct from academic intelligence. Emotional intelligence contains Ability Model, presented by Mayer and Salovey (1997) which is one of the well-known model.

Roseman’s Model of Emotion

Roseman’s model consists of five “appraisal” components. These five components in turn generate 14 types of “Emotions”. The five different appraisal components and the emotions that can be generated are as follows:

1. Motivational State (Appetitive, Aversive)
2. Situational State (Motive Consistent, Motive In-consistent)
3. Probability (Certain, Uncertain, Unknown)
4. Power (Strong, Weak)
5. Agency (Self-Caused, Other-Caused, Circumstantial-Caused).

Intelligence

David Wechsler has defined intelligence as “The aggregate or global capacity of an individual to act purposefully, to think rationally, and to deal effectively with his environment”. It is an innate quality or trait of human beings for better understanding, deciding, problem solving and attaining the goals.

According to Einstein, “The true sign of intelligence is not knowledge but imagination”.

Emotional Intelligence

Emotional intelligence impacts not only the performance but also health of individuals. It is an innate ability or trait of an individual to be aware of his surroundings, to control and express his/her own emotions and use these emotions, judiciously and empathetically to manage interpersonal relationship.

Mayer and Salovey in 1990 first defined Emotional Intelligence as “The Subset of social intelligence that involve the ability to monitor one’s own and others feelings and emotions, to discriminate among them and to use this information to guide one’s thinking and action”.

Mayer and Salovey later in 1997 redefined their previous definitions and said, “The capacity to perceive emotions, to access and generate emotions so as to assist thoughts, to understand emotions and emotional knowledge and to reflectively regulate emotions so as to promote emotional and Intellectual growth”.

Mayer and Salovey later in 2004 once again redefined EI as “The ability to perceive accurately, appraise and express emotions, the ability to access and/or generate feelings when they facilitate thought, the ability to understand emotions and emotional knowledge and the ability to regulate emotions to promote emotional and intellectual growth”.

In addition to providing a more formal definition of EI, the articles of Mayer and Salovey from the year 1990 describe an “Emotional Intelligence Person” to be a “Well-adjusted, genuine, warm, persistent and optimistic person”. Ahmad, Bangash, and Khan (2009) assert that men have higher emotional intelligence than women.

Method

In the present study the investigator tried to understand the influence of gender on the emotional intelligence of sports players of Patna University, the researcher divided the sample into male and female players those who have participated university sports competitions. Further he checked the emotional intelligence and compared between the sample groups of the research study.

Objectives

1. To measure the emotional intelligence of sports players of Patna University.
2. To compare the emotional intelligence between male and female sports players of Patna University.
3. Find out the statistical significance difference in emotional intelligence between male and female sports players.

Hypothesis

1. There will be no significance influence of gender on the emotional intelligence of sports players.
2. There will be no significance difference in emotional intelligence among male and female sports players.

Sample of the study

The researcher selected one hundred sports players those participated in inter collegiate sports competitions of Patna University, both male and female in equal number on simple random method of sampling. They given the needed information about the research study to the sample and provided the standard scale of emotional intelligence to collect the data from sample of the study.

Tools

The emotional Intelligence Scale- EIS, developed by Dr. Arun Kumar Singh, Professor and former head, University department of Psychology and Dr. Shruti Narain, Department of Psychology, Patna Women's College, Patna, Bihar. The scale consisted of 31 items with four divisions: 1. Understanding emotions, 2. Understanding motivation, 3. Empathy, 4. Handling relations.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

The researcher used Statistical Mean, SD and t-tests to interpretation of research data.

Table- 1 Showing the Emotional Intelligence among Male and Female Sports Players of Patna University

Sports Players	N	Mean	SD	t-value
Male	50	26.08	2.79	3.97*
Female	50	23.54	3.59	

* Significant at 0.01 levels

Graph- 1 Showing the Emotional Intelligence among Male and Female Sports Players of Patna University

The table and graph are showing the emotional intelligence between male and female sports players of Patna University, Patna, Bihar. The male sports players mean score in emotional intelligence test is 26.08 and standard deviation is 2.79, the female mean score is 23.54 and standard deviation is 3.59, the calculate t-value is 3.97 which is more than the t-table value 2.67 of degree of freedom 98 at significance level 0.01. The research study revealed that the male sports players are having emotional intelligence while the female sports players are having the average emotional intelligence in their personality.

Conclusion

- The aforementioned study showed that male had greater (EI) than female. Male university students had high level of emotionally self-regulation and emotional self-awareness than their female counter part. But in case of interpersonal skills, male and female university students were equivalent.
- The male sports players having higher emotional intelligence in the study than the female sports players.
- There is significance of difference in emotional intelligence between male and female sports players.

References

- Ahmad, S., Bangash, H., & Khan, S. A. (2009). *Emotional intelligence and gender differences*. *Sarhad Journal of Agricultural*, 25(1), 127-130.
- Banks, J. A. (2012). *Encyclopaedia of Diversity in Education*. SAGE Publications.
- Bar-On, R. (1997). *The emotional quotient inventory (EQ-i) technical manual*. Toronto: Multi-Health Systems, Inc.
- Ciocarell, S. E. & Meyer, G. E. (2006). *Psychology*, Prentice Hall Higher Education.
- Goleman, D. (1996). *Emotional Intelligence- Why it can Matter more than IQ*, New York: Bantam Books.
- Goleman, D. (1998). *Working with Emotional Intelligence*. New York: Bantam Books.
- Mayer, J. D., Salovey, P., & Caruso, D. R. (2000). *Emotional intelligence as zeitgeist, as personality and as a mental ability*. In Bar-On R. & Parker, J. D. A. (Eds.). *The handbook of emotional intelligence: Theory, development, assessment, and application at home, school, and in the workplace*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- Salovey, P. and Mayer, J.D. (1990). *Emotional Intelligence, Imagination, Cognition and Personality*, 9, 185-211.